

EFFECTS OF ARTIFICIAL AGEING ON SEED GERMINATION PERCENTAGE OF SOYBEAN

S. N. Devkule*, R. C. Mahajan, A. D. Pandagale and V. N. Chinchane
 Vasantnao Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani – 431402 (Maharashtra)

sndevkule@gmail.com

MS Received: 04.08.2024; MS Revised: 29.04.2024; MS Accepted: 30.08.2024

MS 3238

(RESEARCH PAPER IN AGRICULTURE,)

Abstract

The present investigation was conducted at the Experimental Farm, Department of Agricultural Botany, VNMKV, Parbhani, the Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, VNMKV, Parbhani, the Quality Control Laboratory, MSSC Ltd., Parbhani and the Department of Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry, College of Agriculture, Golegaon, Hingoli, using soybean varieties MAUS-71, MAUS-158, JS-335, and MAUS-162.

The study on the effects of ageing revealed that the seeds of all varieties (MAUS-71, MAUS-158, JS-335, and MAUS-162) were artificially aged for various durations (24, 48, 72, 96, and 120 hours) at different temperatures (41°C, 42°C, 43°C, 44°C, and 45°C). Among the varieties, MAUS-162 was found to perform better in terms of moisture percentage, germination rate, germination index, seedling length, seed vigor index, and electrical conductivity, as compared to MAUS-71, MAUS-158, and JS-335 at the end of 120 hours of artificial ageing and 240 days of storage.

Additionally, the soybean variety MAUS-162 was superior in terms of biochemical parameters, such as malondialdehyde content, superoxide dismutase activity, peroxide activity, protein content, oil content, and dehydrogenase activity.

Keywords: soybean, ageing, temperature

Introduction

Soybean [*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill] is an important oil crop in the family Leguminosae, subfamily Papilionaceae, and genus *Glycine* L. Soybean is of particular importance in times of energy crisis and closure and plays central role in agriculture, and export. It has now become an oil and seed crop and is the cheapest alternative source of high-quality protein and cooking oil. Soybeans are high in protein and a rich source of carbohydrates and fats. They are a good source of vitamins, minerals and beneficial plant compounds, such as isoflavones. Soybeans have great potential as a particularly nutritious and protein-rich food. In general, stronger seeds can withstand high temperatures and high humidity while producing normal seedlings. Field appearance and seed storage capacity are closely related to seed vigor, which in turn, is negatively affected by different aging periods and storage conditions. The quality of soybean seeds is easily degraded, making it difficult to preserve for a long time. The physiological properties and storage capacity of seeds are influenced by humidity, which in-turn is controlled by the relative humidity of the surrounding air. Seeds are hygroscopic, they tend to absorb or lose moisture causing various biochemical changes in soybeans.

Materials and Methods

The present investigation was carried out aiming at assessment of seed viability of plant species with high oil content and germination after seed had been stored and aged for certain period. Based on the aged seed vigour assessment, we can establish its field emergence capacity and possibility of forming vigorous and healthy plants which will be high yielding. The experimental material for the present investigation consists of four soybeans (*Glycine max* (L.) Merrill.) varieties representing two maturity groups viz., MAUS-71 and MAUS-158 (Early maturity group: 93-95 days) and JS-335 and MAUS-162 (Late maturity group: 95-103 days). The seed material was evaluated for different seed quality parameters under natural and accelerated ageing conditions. Seed quality parameters were judged at 0, 60, 120, 180 and 240 days of storage.

Results and Discussion

The data on effect of varieties, temperature and storage hours on germination of soybean seed during artificial ageing are presented in Table 1 and Fig. 1

The data revealed that the mean germination percentage influenced significantly during all the storage periods. It was also noticed that seed germination percent decreased with the advancement of storage period irrespective of varieties, temperature and storage hours.

The significant differences in germination percentage of varieties were observed during all the storage periods irrespective of temperature and

storage hours. The initial mean germination percent of MAUS-162, MAUS-158, MAUS-71 and JS-335 was 91.33, 88.66, 88.33 and 83.33 percentages, respectively.

The soybean variety, MAUS-162 showed significantly higher (86.33, 82.00 %) seed germination percent than MAUS-158 (82.66, 80.00 %), MAUS-71 (81.66, 77.33 %) and JS-335 (79.00, 76.66 %) AA at 42°C and 43°C storage temperature.

The germination from all the varieties of soybean showed minimum seed certification standard for germination MAUS-162 (72.00 %) MAUS-158 (71.33 %), MAUS-71 (69.66 %) and JS-335 (42.66 %) i.e. 70% at AA for 72 hrs. and 43 °C temperature of storage periods, identified the transition point for soybean seed quality, after which germination decreased sharply.

The highest germination percentage was recorded at 24 hrs. and 41°C temperature of accelerated ageing period where as the lowest germination was observed at 120 hrs. and 45°C temperature of accelerated ageing period.

It is evident from Table 1 that as the duration and temperature of accelerated ageing increased, the percent germination of all four varieties decreased throughout the entire duration of accelerated ageing among the treatments, 24 hrs. and 41°C temperature of accelerated ageing recorded high germination percentage MAUS-162, MAUS-158, MAUS-71 and JS-335 was 91.33, 88.66, 88.33 and 83.33 percentages, respectively. The present results are also in agreement with Shantappa *et al.*, (2006) in bitter gourd, Singh and Kanaujia (2006) in rice and Geeta and Singh (2007) in pea. Findings are confirmed by Egli *et al.*, (1979), Gregg (1982), Gupta and Aneja (2004) and Toledo *et al.*, (2010).

References

1. Egli, D. B., White, G. M. & Tekrony, D. M. (1979). Relationship between seed vigour and storability of soybean seed. *J. Seed Tech.*, 3: 1- 11.
2. Geeta, B. & Singh, M. (2007). Seed storage potential using natural and accelerated ageing in pea. *Seed Research*. 35:198-220.
3. Gregg, B. R. (1982). Soybean seed quality and practical storage. In soybean seed quality and stand establish (Eds.) J. B. Sinclair and J. A. Jacobs, University of Illinois, Urbana, Illinois. *INTSOY series no. 22*: 52-56.
4. Gupta, A. & Aneja, K. R. (2004). Seed deterioration in soybean varieties during storage - physiological attributes. *Seed Res.* 32(1): 26-32.
5. Shantappa, T., Shekhargouda, M., Merwade, M. N., Laxman Kukanoor & Bellad, S. B. (2006). Seed quality as

- influenced by Accelerated and Natural Ageing in Bitter Gourd. Seed research 34: 66-69.
6. **Singh, C. B. & Kanaujia, V. P. (2006).** Germination and seed vigour in accelerated aged seeds of rice (*Oryza sativa* L.). *Seed Research*, 34:70-73. ,
 7. **S. N. Devkule*, R. C. Mahajan, H.V. Kalpande And G. W. Narkhede, 2022,** Effects Of Artificial Ageing On Seed Moisture Percentage Of Soybean, Vol. Xii, Issue Xxxiv, Oct 2022 Multilogic In Science Issn 2277-7601, Pag 261-264.
 8. **Toledo, M. Z., Cavariani, C., Franca-Neto, J. B. and Nakagawa, J. (2010).** Imbibition damage in soybean seed as affected by initial moisturecontent, cultivar and production of locations. *Seed Sci. and tech.*, 38 (2): 399-408.

Table 1: Effect of artificial ageing on seed germination percentage of soybean varieties V X T X H Mean Table

	V1=MAUS-71					V2=MAUS-158					V3=JS-335					V4=MAUS-162				
	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5
H1	88.33	81.67	77.33	72.67	69.33	88.67	82.67	80.00	74.00	67.67	83.33	79.00	76.67	69.00	70.67	91.33	86.33	82.00	76.33	72.33
H2	84.67	76.00	72.67	63.00	58.33	85.33	77.33	76.33	64.67	55.67	78.67	69.33	62.33	48.33	45.33	88.00	80.33	76.67	55.00	46.67
H3	76.33	70.33	69.67	58.00	44.67	77.67	72.00	71.33	60.67	41.33	75.00	51.00	42.67	39.00	32.00	84.33	78.00	72.00	44.00	41.00
H4	70.00	63.67	59.00	41.33	27.33	72.33	66.00	62.33	40.33	22.00	64.33	39.67	28.33	22.33	16.00	80.67	69.67	65.33	25.33	22.67
H5	63.00	47.33	42.33	34.67	15.67	65.00	52.33	47.67	29.00	16.00	50.00	31.33	19.00	14.67	9.67	71.67	56.67	49.00	18.33	16.67

Note V = Variety V1=MAUS-71, V2=MAUS-158, V3=JS-335, V4=MAUS-162
 T = Temperature T1=41 °C, T2=42 °C, T3=43 °C, T4=44 °C, T5=45 °C
 H = Hours H1=24hrs., H2= 48hrs., H3=72hrs., H4=96hrs., H5=120 hrs.

Table Of Sem, Sed And C.D.

Factors	C.D.	SE(d)	SE(m)
Factor(V)	0.47	0.24	0.17
Factor(T)	0.53	0.27	0.19
Interaction V X T	1.05	0.53	0.38
Factor(H)	0.53	0.27	0.19
Interaction V X H	1.05	0.53	0.38
Interaction T X H	1.18	0.60	0.42
Interaction V X T X H	2.35	1.19	0.84

Note: V = Variety V1=MAUS-71 V2=MAUS-158, V3=JS-335, V4=MAUS-162
 T = Temperature T1=41 °C, T2=42 °C, T3=43 °C, T4=44 °C, T5=45 °C
 H = Hours H1=24hrs., H2=48hrs., H3=72hrs., H4=96hrs., H5=120 hrs.

Fig. 1: Effect of artificial ageing on seed germination percentage of soybean varieties

Note : V = Variety V1=MAUS-71 V2=MAUS-158, V3=JS-335, V4=MAUS-162
 T = Temperature T1=41 °C, T2=42 °C, T3=43 °C, T4=44 °C, T5=45 °C
 H = Hours H1=24hrs., H2=48hrs., H3=72hrs., H4=96hrs., H5=120 hrs.

	T1	T2	T3	T4	T5	Mean V
V1=MAUS-71	76.47	67.80	64.20	53.93	43.07	61.09
V2=MAUS-158	77.80	70.07	67.53	53.73	40.53	61.93
V3=JS-335	70.27	54.07	45.80	38.67	34.73	48.71
V4=MAUS-162	83.20	74.20	69.00	43.80	39.87	62.01
Mean T	76.93	66.53	61.63	47.53	39.55	

Note VxH Variety
 T = Temperature
 H = Hours
 V1=MAUS-71 V2=MAUS-158, V3=JS-335, V4=MAUS-162
 T1=41 °C, T2=42 °C, T3=43 °C, T4=44 °C, T5=45 °C
 H1=24hrs., H2=48hrs., H3=72hrs., H4=96hrs., H5=120 hrs.

	H1	H2	H3	H4	H5	Mean V
V1=MAUS-71	77.87	70.93	63.80	52.27	40.60	61.09
V2=MAUS-158	78.60	71.87	64.60	52.60	42.00	61.93
V3=JS-335	75.73	60.80	47.93	34.13	24.93	48.71
V4=MAUS-162	81.67	69.33	63.87	52.73	42.47	62.01
Mean H	78.47	68.23	60.05	47.93	37.50	

Note: V = Variety
 T = Temperature
 H = Hours
 V1=MAUS-71 V2=MAUS-158, V3=JS-335, V4=MAUS-162
 T1=41 °C, T2=42 °C, T3=43 °C, T4=44 °C, T5=45 °C
 H1=24hrs., H2=48hrs., H3=72hrs., H4=96hrs., H5=120 hrs.